

OXYFUEL COMBUSTION OF BIOGENIC LOW CALORIFIC VALUE GASES – INFLUENCE OF WATER INJECTION ON COMBUSTION CHARACTERISTICS AND EXHAUST GAS COMPOSITION

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ABSTRACT: Oxyfuel combustion describes the combustion of a fuel with pure oxygen. Idealized, the exhaust gas consists only of CO₂ and H₂O. A high-purity CO₂ point source can be created by condensing water. The technology is therefore very suitable for CCUS. One possibility for moderating the combustion chamber temperature in oxyfuel combustion is the injection of liquid water. In this paper, the influence of water injection on the flue gas composition and emissions during oxyfuel combustion of a biogas-like CH₄-CO₂ mixture is analyzed. The experimental investigations are carried out on an oxyfuel plant of around 50 kW with downstream flue gas cooling for water vapor separation and flue gas recirculation. In addition, the combustion process is modeled using CFD. A CO₂ content of 93-94.8 vol.% is achieved in the experimental tests. The injection of water proves to be a very efficient cooling strategy for the combustion chamber. The numerical simulation shows that the CO burnout is boosted by the injection of liquid water. In the next steps, an adsorption column for flue gas drying will be installed and the oxyfuel system will be coupled with a pyrolysis reactor.

Keywords: bioenergy, oxyfuel, CO₂ capture, combustion, carbon dioxide, biogas

1 INTRODUCTION

Oxyfuel combustion is a promising technology to enable Carbon Capture, Utilization and Storage (CCUS). It uses pure oxygen as an oxidizer – instead of air. Hence the flue gas consists mainly of CO₂ and H₂O. Downstream flue gas cooling leads to condensation of the water vapor and thus a flue gas stream with a very high CO₂ concentration remains. This CO₂ can be captured easily and made available for utilization or storage. If a biogenic fuel, e.g. biogas, is used and the captured CO₂ is stored permanently, this can be referred to as Bioenergy with Carbon Capture and Storage (BECCS). This type of CO₂-negative process is considered necessary by the IPCC in most of the scenarios to limit global warming to 1.5 °C [1]. However, traditional combustion of low calorific gases, such as most biogenic gases, in an oxyfuel atmosphere causes issues with combustion stability [2]. Flameless combustion can counteract this problem. In flameless combustion, the oxidizer is injected into the combustion chamber with a high velocity. The high momentum of the jet causes large quantities of surrounding hot flue gas to be entrained and mixed with the reactants. This leads the mixture to exceed the auto-ignition temperature and reactants are intensively diluted. A large-volume reaction without a visible flame front occurs. As there is no flame front in the conventional sense, it does not need to be stabilized. To ensure a stable combustion, the momentum of the oxidizer only needs to be sufficient to entrain enough hot exhaust gas [3]. The combustion reaction leads to the release of heat and thus to an increase in temperature, which can reach 1500 °C and more in an adiabatic combustion chamber. As the materials of the combustion chamber and the burner cannot withstand such high temperatures, it must be moderated. One option is to inject liquid water into the combustion chamber. Utilizing the enthalpy of vaporization for cooling is highly efficient. In addition, the condensation enthalpy can be reused when separating the water vapor in the oxyfuel process. There are many possible uses for the CO₂ captured after oxyfuel combustion. It can be used as a feedstock for methanol synthesis or methanation or as a starting material for other chemicals. It can also be fed into pipelines for

underground storage. All these applications place certain demands on the purity of the CO₂. The purity of the CO₂ in oxyfuel combustion is significantly influenced by impurities in the fuel and oxidizer, by leakage of ambient air and by the oxyfuel process itself. The latter refers to the formation of CO and the retention of residual O₂ due to incomplete combustion and the retention of residual H₂O due to incomplete condensation. Two specific objectives were designated for the present study: On the one hand to experimentally determine the CO₂ concentration in the flue gas during oxyfuel combustion of a biogas-like fuel with downstream flue gas cooling. On the other hand, to investigate the influence of water injection in the combustion chamber on the flue gas composition and chemical reaction.

2 METHODS AND EXPERIMENTS

This section describes the methodology used to obtain the experimental and numerical results.

2.1 Oxyfuel plant and experimental procedure

An oxyfuel plant in a scale of 50 kW was set up at Fraunhofer UMSICHT to enable experimental investigations to be carried out. The system consists of a combustion chamber, a two-stage flue gas cooling system, an exhaust gas fan, a recirculation fan and an injection system for liquid water. Figure 1 shows a scheme of the plant.

Figure 1: Scheme of the oxyfuel plant at Fraunhofer UMSICHT

As the combustion process is flameless, it is possible to change fuel and oxidizer composition without having to make any changes to the burner system. The fuel and the oxidizer are fed into the combustion chamber separately. The oxidizer consists of a mixture of pure oxygen and recirculated exhaust gas, whereby the oxygen content in the exhaust gas can be varied by the amount of recirculated flue gas. Fuel and oxygen react in large volumes, as is typical for flameless combustion. Liquid water injection enables temperature moderation. The flue gas exits the combustion chamber through the burner, preheating the oxidizer. In a first step, the exhaust gas is cooled down to approx. 120 °C in a heat exchanger to provide heat at a high temperature level. Afterwards it is subcooled in the condenser to 20 °C and water is separated. Part of the dry flue gas is recirculated to the combustion chamber and oxygenated. The other part is conveyed out of the system with the aid of the flue gas fan.

For this work, the plant was operated with a power of 40 kW and a biogas-like mixture of natural gas and CO₂ as a fuel. Two operating points were defined. These differ in the amount of recirculated exhaust gas and the amount of injected water. The settings for the two operating points (OP I and OP II) are listed in Table I.

Table I: Settings for experimental investigations

Parameter	OP I	OP II
Power	40 kW	
Fuel	CH ₄ -CO ₂ mixture (60/40)	
T Combustion	1050 °C	
λ	1 – 1.05	
O ₂ Oxidizer	23 vol.% O ₂	13 vol.% O ₂
Recirculation	25 m ³ /h	50 m ³ /h
Water Injection	19.5 kg/h	11.2 kg/h
T Exhaust	20 °C	

The exhaust gas composition and emissions are measured using an online FTIR analyzer.

2.2 Numerical model

The present CFD simulation adopts a 3D computational domain of the burner and the cylindrical combustion chamber. It contains approx. one million cells. Commercial software ANSYS Fluent is used to solve the differential equations of the RANS simulation. The standard $k - \epsilon$ model is adopted to solve the turbulence. To take into account the radiation of the hot gases in the combustion chamber the discrete ordinates model (DO) with weight-sum-gray-gas (WSGG) model is used. The eddy dissipation concept (EDC) model and reduced mechanism DRM22 (derived from GRI-Mech 3.0) [4] are applied to solve the turbulence-chemistry interaction. Water injection is implemented via Discrete Phase Injection. The boundary conditions at the inlet and outlet were selected based on OP I. The combustion chamber is assumed to be adiabatic. For a better understanding of the results, the combustion chamber with the position of the burner and the position of the water injection is modelled in Figure 2.

3 RESULTS

Firstly, the experimental results are shown. This includes the measured exhaust gas composition at Operating Point

I and Operating Point II as well as the correlation between the measured CO emissions and the residual O₂ in the exhaust gas. For a better comparison of the CO emissions at different O₂ contents in the oxidizer of OP I and OP II, CO emissions are related to the output and stated in mg/MJ. The numerical simulation of the combustion process is then discussed. It is shown how the water injection influences the chemical reaction sequence of the combustion process.

Figure 2: Model of the cylindric combustion chamber with burner and position of water injection. The water is injected radially via lances with nozzles. The openings for the lances are each offset by 120 °

3.1 Experimental results

The flue gas composition at OP I and OP II is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Flue gas composition measured after condensation for a) operating point I and b) operating point II

At the same excess O₂ of 0.91 vol.%, a CO₂ content of 93 vol.% is measured in OP I and 94.8 vol.% in OP II. The residual H₂O content is higher in OP I than in OP II. This is due to the larger amount of liquid water that is injected in OP I. The nitrogen content is approximately the same in both cases. This small amount is unavoidable as it is part of the natural gas used for the experiments.

Figure 4 shows the correlation between the measured excess oxygen in the flue gas and the CO emissions. The CO emissions increase more with lower excess oxygen in OP I than in OP II. However, this is probably not due to the varying amount of injected water, but rather to the higher volume flow of exhaust gas recirculated in OP II.

This leads to greater turbulent mixing in the combustion chamber, which improves burnout.

Figure 4: Correlation between excess oxygen and CO emissions at Operating Point I and Operating Point II

3.2 Numerical results

The main reaction pathway of methane oxidation is $\text{CH}_4 \rightarrow \text{CH}_3 \rightarrow \text{CH}_2\text{O} \rightarrow \text{HCO} \rightarrow \text{CO} \rightarrow \text{CO}_2$. The last step, i.e. the burnout of CO to CO_2 , is mainly carried out by the reaction of CO with OH radicals $\text{CO} + \text{OH} \rightleftharpoons \text{CO}_2 + \text{H}$. In oxyfuel combustion, the very high CO_2 concentrations in the combustion chamber cause CO_2 to react more with H radicals, thus shifting the equilibrium of the above reaction to the left. This leads to increased CO emissions due to reduced burnout [5]. Figure 5 shows the rate of this reaction.

Figure 5: Kinetic rate of reaction $\text{CO} + \text{OH} \rightleftharpoons \text{CO}_2 + \text{H}$. The contour plot shows the radial section of the combustion chamber at the height of the water injection points

The conversion of CO to CO_2 is highest at the three points where the water is injected. On the one hand, this is due to the reduced CO_2 concentration at the injection points. On the other hand, water is a source of OH radicals which are responsible for the burnout of CO. This observation is also reflected in the distribution of the molar CO_2 concentration in the combustion chamber, which is shown in Figure 6. The highest concentration of CO_2 in this section appears at the position of water injection. This indicates the promoted CO burnout through water injection.

4 CONCLUSION AND OUTLOOK

Experimental and numerical investigations were carried out on the oxyfuel combustion of a low calorific, biogas-like fuel with downstream flue gas cooling on a scale of 40 kW. In the experimental investigations, two operating points were considered at which a different

amount of water was injected into the combustion chamber and a varying amount of exhaust gas was recirculated.

Figure 6: Molar concentration of CO_2 in the radial section of the combustion chamber at the height of water injection.

A CO_2 content of 93 - 94.8 vol.% was achieved. The H_2O content in the flue gas is higher the more water is injected into the combustion chamber. The CO emissions appear to be lower with the same residual oxygen content in the case of a higher flue gas recirculation rate. This is presumably due to better turbulent mixing in the combustion chamber. The numerical calculations show that the CO burnout is boosted by the water injection. This is mainly due to the shift of the equilibrium to the right during the reaction $\text{CO} + \text{OH} \rightleftharpoons \text{CO}_2 + \text{H}$. The next step is to implement downstream adsorption on the system. This is intended to remove the residual water vapor. The system will also be coupled with a biomass pyrolysis reactor for the combustion of biogenic pyrolysis gas. This makes it possible to demonstrate a CO_2 -negative process if the captured CO_2 is permanently stored.

5 REFERENCES

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9 ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

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